

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B095
Date: 13 May 2005
Take Off 09:47:15
Landing: 13:50:54
Flight Time 4h03m39

Campaign: CLOPAP
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: North Sea (southern area)

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Charlie Whittaker	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	BAES
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	CCN /CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
7	CCN Training	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Cloud Physics	Martin Pickering	Met Office
10	ADA/CPI	Mike Flynn	University of Manchester
11	AMS	James Allan	University of Manchester
12	WAS	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
13	NOXY	Dave Stewart	UEA
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B095 Track 13-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b095
 Date: 13/5/05
 Project: CLOPAP
 Location: North Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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094046		taxy start	0.13 kft	054	
094715		T/O	0.12 kft	032	from cranfield
094926		asp open	3.4 kft	036	
095443		jw nevz zero	6.0 kft	153	
102830	103132	Profile 1	-.17 - 2.6 kft	016	
103929	104948	Run 1	1.1 kft	181	below cloud
105244	110245	Run 2	1.6 kft	004	in cloud
110553	111554	Run 3	2.4 kft	172	above cloud
112959	113304	Profile 2	-.25 - 2.4 kft	357	
114118	115116	Run 4	1.2 kft	172	below cloud
115447	120447	Run 5	1.8 kft	008	in cloud
120905	122000	Run 6	2.8 kft	181	above cloud
123550	123910	Profile 3	-.29 - 2.6 kft	002	
124753	125752	Run 7	1.0 kft	180	below cloud
130101	131101	Run 8	1.9 kft	003	in cloud
131405	132633	Run 9	2.7 kft	178	above cloud
134135		asp closed	6.3 kft	236	
135054		Land	0.17 kft	000	at cranfield
135650		standstill	0.16 kft	000	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B095 Track 13-MAY-05

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP (Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud) : T.W.Choularton/|KNB

Scientific Aims:

1. To investigate the evolution of an urban plume as it is advected to the northeast over East Anglia and the North Sea in cloudy conditions. Changes in chemical speciation and the partitioning of species between the gas and particulate phases will be investigated.
2. To measure the changes in the size distribution and Cloud Condensation Nucleus (CCN) activity spectrum of the aerosol.
3. To measure changes in cloud microphysics as the aerosol properties in the plume change, particularly those of the sub-set of aerosol acting as CCN.
4. To investigate the differences in the composition of aerosol that form cloud droplets and those that remain unactivated and interstitial to the cloud, and to observe how this changes as the plume ages.
5. To investigate the role of vertical exchange between the boundary layer and the free troposphere to understand its effect on the transport of aerosols and trace gases on the cloudy plume.

Weather conditions

A stratocumulus capped boundary layer forming over the sea downwind of a main source of air pollution. Limited convective penetration of the boundary layer top is acceptable (but not deep convection). The cloud cover should exceed 70% in the study areas.

Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

All instruments to be operated continuously.

1) Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations,
- ADA – as above
- CCN* - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample per run, if possible.
- Ice Nucleus counter* (INC) normally operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to a different set of conditions.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- TWC – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

Chemistry Measurements

- 2) WAS - 2 bottle samples per 10min flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist.
- 3) NO_x, Ozone, SO₂, CO, PTRMS, Hydrogen peroxide to operate continuously.
- 4) AMS - to be operated on Rosemount inlet out of cloud, CVI inlet in cloud if possible. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.
- 5) Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rear.

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud

Flight Number : B095

Date: 13th May 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To study the evolution of aerosol in cloud as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol with cloud both as the aerosol modifies the cloud microphysics and the cloud modifies the aerosol.

Sortie Location: Area of low cloud over the western N Sea, looking at the interaction with air advecting westwards from the continent. The cloud region is expected to be present from the east coast of England and out eastwards of the Wash area into the North Sea. The flying should start either at the upwind cloud edge or as far out upwind (eastwards) as possible (up to 200 km).

Sortie Summary: The case studies will be carried out by flying a series of 100 km transects (straight and level runs – SLRs) across the plume within the boundary layer, one below cloud, one in cloud and one in the lower free troposphere immediately above cloud top. Each of these sets of transects will be immediately preceded by a vertical profile extending into the lower free troposphere starting from as close to the surface as possible. These profiles will establish the vertical mixing and structure of the sampled air and establish the optimum altitudes for the following transects. This flight pattern will be repeated at intervals of about 50km downwind to obtain up to 4 sets of transects. Although we are not aiming to perform a comprehensive Lagrangian study, this flight plan will allow us to approximately track the same air as it is advects downwind of the source region and to examine its evolution as it interacts with the low cloud.

Sortie Detail

- a) Take off and climb to FL 110 for transit at cruise speed to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent carrying out NO_x calibration at that level)
- b) T+ 55 When starting region is reached over N. Sea (upwind E edge of cloud bank or 200km out) descend to minimum safe altitude below cloud. Perform profile ascent P1 (at 1000 ft per minute) to pass through cloud layer to an altitude 100 ft above cloud top and the boundary layer top.
- c) T+ 73 Descend (not profile descent) to below cloud base, perform a straight and level run below cloud base (200 ft below cloud base) across wind for about 100 km (or long enough for measurements / calibrations to be made - 12 mins) - mission scientist to announce “out of cloud” transect at start.
- d) T+ 90 Ascend to the middle of the cloud layer. Turn through 180 degrees. Perform a straight and level run of length 100 km (or less – say 12 mins) across wind in cloud) (if cloud layer deep enough mission scientist may request 2 in cloud transects one near cloud base one near cloud top) - Mission Scientist to announce “in cloud” transect at start.
- e) T+104 Ascend to 200 feet above cloud top, turn through 180 degrees, and perform straight and level run of length 100 km (or less – say 12 mins) across wind - Mission scientist to announce “out of cloud” transect at start.
- f) T+118 Ascend (if required) and cruise to 50 km downwind of initial stack of SLRs and repeat b to e.
- g) Ascend to transit level to travel a further 50 km downwind and repeat b to e
- h) Continue repetitions until available flight time in science area is exhausted
- i) T+240 Climb to transit level to return to home base (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)
- j) T+280 Land.

Mission Scientist's Log

(MSci - Keith Bower)

Flight No **B.095**.....

Date 13/05/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:56:24	Transit	8'000	44	52.2N/0.0E	P 747mb T/Td -S 07/-25.86°C Gms/55°
09:59:04					Can start NOXY cal (at science speed now) - NOXY <small>reverts delay</small>
10:10:20	Trans.	8000	79	57.2/1.2	7mins to go on NOXY cal 4ms/82° -8.73°/-31.23°C ADA✓ AMS✓ ZDV✓
10:10:47	TJ	FL110	66	52.9/2.0	NOXY cal complete, -9.12/-23.84°C 4ms/71°
10:21:39					descent to 2500' - start - broken Sc below.
10:25:00					CT ~ 3000' - Captain into CT. - v. thin deck. - clear below
10:28:06				53.3/2.3	100'
✓ 10:28:30	P1				50' and drinking profile P1
10:29:56		1.0 kft			Cloud - wispy
10:30:20	sh.	1680 ft	captain		enters cloud
10:31		2350 ft			CT. - occasional bubble up to 2500
10:31:32	P1	2 3000			and P1
10:33:49				53.7.23	descend to below cloud 1st Run at 1400
10:38:23					at 1400' and timing: core chem cal starting.
10:39:29	R1 _{start}	1400'			1400' - right at edge of cloud layer above.
10:41:25	R1	1400			Chem (core) cal complete - WAS bottle & stick
10:42:33	R1	1400	176	57.7/2.3	4.1°C/2.25°C 11ms/53° 973mb (212kts)
10:44:29	R1				2 Photos below deck - closer to CB - down
10:45:05	R1				to 1450' ^(ago) 1/2 mins into cloud - ZD bricks
10:46:05	R1		173		cen - complete - good.
10:47:05	R1				Photo - of lower CB base
					1700-1800' - Captain about best level for next
					in cloud (but tachy - CB changing with x)

Mission Scientist's Log

(M. Sci Kath Brown)

Flight No **B.095**.....

Date 13/05/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:49:38	end R1	1400			2D. descend somewhat ↑, 450 from 250 at N end
10:51:30					go up another. AMS change over to CVI complete
10:52:44	st R2	1850'			In cloud - Core Chem Cal started.
10:53:20	R2	1850	9°	53.2/23	9ms/65° 2.73°/2.88°C
					low cores of drizzle drops (cont'd updating every 500m)
					CPI - some drops = 30µm, ADA seen drops on PI
					On CVI now on AMS - no particles CVI change stagnation period
10:56:08					Core Chem Calc ✓ (too small to catch drops)
10:57:59	R2	1650	05°	53.4/23	2.71/2.94°C, 8ms/52°, 957mb
					still is so thin
10:59:50					middle of cloud layer - 200' thick
10:59:55					just come out of cloud
11:01:17					a few blobs of cloud. (11:02:40 too)
11:02:45	end R2				now up to 2500' scattered, 200' above cloud
					few particles on AMS (PC).
11:49:09					at 2500' - still some cloud - climb another 200'
11:05:53	st R3	2700			still some wispy cl
11:06:22					AMS out Rosemond inlet
11:07:42					now above CT - do CCN measurement
11:08:18	R3	2700	176	53.6/2.3E	4.08°C / -5.49°C 12ms/49° 929mb.
11:09:08					Core Chem Calc ✓ WAS starts
11:09:50					Photo 20@ 11:11:44.
11:13:35		capt.			CT rising a bit - skimming through TOPS
					begin to grow a little bit while operating - now gone
11:15:03					CCN done - 1 min to run

Mission Scientist's Log

(MSi: Keith Bower)

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Date **13/05/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:15:54	end T3	2700		53.1/2.3E	3.69 / -7.16°C - climbing to 5000' Toilet Break!
	transit to next	stuck 500m downward			Got some higher level cloud above us (T+ 88 mins is ahead of schedule by 16mins)
11:21:56	T2				Photo on transit
11:25:26					descending to get to start of P2
11:27:10		2300'			Going through cloud @ CT.
11:27:45		1700'			CB.
11:29:59	P2 start	50' ↑		53.2/1.5°	Start of profile ascent
		1750 (cepl)		S3	CB ~ 1750'
		2200 (me)			CT ~ 2200 (peaks at 2500')
11:33:04	end P2		11deg	53.4/1.4	descending to 1500' for below cloud run CT at 2350 (me) CB at 1800 (me)
11:36:53		1500			Photo Below CB @ 1500' - Core then start cals
11:39:20					into CB now but turning around to do R4
11:40:31	R4	1500			Core Chem Cals ✓
11:41:16	st R4	1500	176	53.7/1.5°E	15 mts / 49° 3.98°C / 2.53°C 970mb
11:43:10	R4	1500	173		2 photos WAS bottle confirm stated.
11:46:13	R4				CB is higher here
11:48:07	R4	1500	175	53.3N/1.5E	CEN completed (213mts) 3.9/3.28°C 15m/39°
11:51:16	end R4	1500			end R4 - climb just over 2000
11:52:37					AMS inlet → CVI comp
11:54:47	st R5	2050'	6	53.1/1.5E	In cloud run started - CORE Chem No Cal + (CVI reports portlets)
11:56:19	R5	2050	2	53.1/1.5	2.1/2.74°C 11m/68 949mb
12:00:09	R5	2050	5	53.4/1.5	Out of Cloud - Gas - More Cloud ahead
12:01:22	R5	2050			Back in Cloud

01.45

Out again - Broken Se

Mission Scientist's Log

(M.Sci: Keith Bower)

Flight No **B.095**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:04:47	end R5	2050		53.6/1.5	Now dumb to 2800 - run N-S - need a bit higher
12:09:05	→ R6	3100			AMS Change Inlet, Core Chem Cal Started
12:09:52	R6	3100	172	53.5/1.5	AMS on Rosemount 3.76/-4.39°C 11m/s/54° 914mb
12:12:36	R6	3100			Core Chem Cals ✓
12:14:15	R6	3100	173	53.3/1.5	3 Photos at CT. 210kts 3.42/-43.82°C 12m/s/54°
12:15:47	R6				CCN - looks good again - finished Core Chem continued to WAS finished
12:20:00	end R6				WAS needed more time for bottle - SC broken below
12:20:30	T3			52.9/1.5E	Will dumb now (3.81°C/-23.7°C, 8m/s/56)
12:31:20				53.0/0.9E	descends to profile start.
12:32:5					CT ≈ 2300', CB ≈ 1700'
12:35:41 ⁵⁰	P3	50' ↑	1°	53.5/0.9	50' and climbing to P3 - 3 photos at 50'
12:38:06	P3	1850'			CB at 1850' (cont)
12:38:55	P3	2700'			CT at 2700'
12:39:10	end P3	3000'		53.4/0	end P1 (ETA Clouds 1500 level) - agree need to go down another 200' to clear CB level Core Chem Cals start now ahead of run by 1m.
12:47:30					turning R into N-S by below cloud - mid turn.
(N-S) 12:47:53	→ R7	1300'		53.8/0.9	Below Cloud p = 977mb 4.69°/2.9°C 14m/s/47°
12:48:47	R7	1300	171		Core Chem Cal ✓ WAS starts. (977 mb)
12:52:15			176	53.5/0.9	2 photos Below Cloud (15m/s/54°, 4.72/2.0°C)
12:56:37			173	53.2/0.9	CCN finished spectrum (Cont - 2250' included)
12:57:52	end R7			53.2/0.9	- climbing to 2250' for uncloud run
12:59:09					AMS inlet changed to CV1 - getting N ₂ O's on CPC too
13:01:01	st R8	2250'	10°	53.1/0.9E	Core Chem - No Cal - WAS to start 914.5mb 2.01°/2.38°
13:03:45			4°		Can see through CB to sea below - thick above.

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	Y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	52	130	140
POST FLIGHT	43	130	139

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.35	0.4	0.076	1.094	0.482
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
Synced 07:44:15	33.15	1.13	7.06	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NO (ppbV)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NO₂ (ppbV)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NO_x (ppbV)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SO₂ (ppbV)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

CO inst. Hung sometime around brief so rebooted @ 08:23:50
 09:33 – SO2 lamp voltage alarm; voltage too high (1255V actual, 1200V max). Rebooted but still read high (1250-1255V)

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)
	12 May 2005 13:08:35	80.95	82.40	6670.07

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
10:04:05	FL110 (630-590)	91.52	77.87	7126.76	46.32	7.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		34.00	-	-	1.075	0.066	0.339
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
10:11		CO valve switch					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
10:16:49	FL110 (493-500)	88.06	79.23	6976.37	48.15	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		34.01	-	-	1.078	0.066	0.339
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
10:32:10		CO valve switch gave value 506 ∴ no need to do full cal					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
10:41:13	FL014	85.23	81.20	6920.93	49.53	7.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.98	-	-	1.114	0.069	0.466
Time	Flight Level	CO					
Time	Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		85.00	81.03	6887.56	49.49	7.10	
10:55:50	FL018 (SO2 lamp voltage 1287V)	Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	-	-	1.114	0.066	0.462
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
11:05:		CO valve switch gave values 514 as a/c climbed					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
11:08:59	FL027	84.58	81.11	6860.53	49.95	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.83	-	-	1.116	0.066	0.451
Time	Flight Level	CO					
Time	Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		84.85	81.22	6891.19	49.80	7.15	
11:40:22	1500'	Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.93	-	-	1.110	0.068	0.465

Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
11:55:		CO valve switch gave value 520 ∴ no need to do full cal Valve didn't reset so values are of cal gas until 12:04:08					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
12:12:03	()	84.57	81.19	6950.74	49.75	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.91	-	-	1.117	0.067	0.446
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
12:48:41	1300'	84.94	81.21	6898.42	49.62	7.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	-	-	1.116	0.069	0.468
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
12:59:		CO valve switch check OK – no req. for full cal					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
13:16:49	FL030	85.20	80.63	6869.09	49.53	7.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.95	-	-	1.114	0.066	0.448
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
	()						
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample

FLIGHT NUMBER: B95	DATE: 13 May 2005	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	Page 4 of 4
PROJECT: CLOPAP North Sea (southern area)			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B095

Date: 24/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
10:28:20	600	0.08	26	10							Start Profile 1 from 50'
10:29:52	300	0.08		20							FL010
10:30:28	25	0.08	31	1							FL020
10:31:32	20	0.08									End of Profile 1 @ 3000'
10:39:30											Start Run 1 @ 1400'
10:40:00	250	0.08	53	10							
10:42:00	230	0.08		10							
10:44:00	400	0.08		40							
10:46:00	350	0.08		40							
10:48:00	470	0.08		60							
10:49:50											End of Run 1
10:52:43											Start Run 2 @ 1900'
10:53:00	300	0.14	58	60	2	50	12				
10:55:00	450	0.10	71	2000	6	50	12				
10:57:00	270	0.25	125	3000	1						
10:59:00	300	0.08	157	2000	1	25	12				
11:01:00	200	0.08	172	15							
11:02:45											End of Run 2
11:05:53											Start Run 3 @ 2700'
11:06:00	55	0.1	227	5							
11:08:00	35	0.08		1							
11:10:00	30	0.08		1							
11:12:00	20	0.08		1							
11:14:00	35	0.08		1							
11:15:56											End of Run 3
11:29:57	270	0.08	269	30							Start Profile 2 from 50'
11:31:28	300	0.08		40							FL010
11:32:40	35	0.08	304	1							FL020
11:33:04											End of Profile 2 @ 2800'
11:41:16											Start Run 4 @ 1500'
11:42:00	220	0.09	341	10							
11:44:00	250	0.09		20							
11:46:00	240	0.08		20							
11:48:00	340	0.08		50							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B095

Date: 24/05/05

Operator: MAP

Page 2 of 3

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:50:00	270	0.08	342	50							
11:51:15											End of Run 4
11:54:49											Start Run 5 @ 2050'
11:55:00	380	0.17	420	2000	8	50	12				
11:57:00	200	0.28	532	3000	1	50	12				
11:59:00	200	0.44	703	4000	5	50	12				
12:01:00	190	0.08	2	500	1						FFSSP restarted due to frozen
12:03:00	150	0.2	19	30							Display. B095A
12:04:52											End of Run 5
12:09:05											Start Run 6 @ 2800'
12:10:00	20	0.07	67								
12:12:00	15	0.08									
12:14:00	20	0.08									
12:16:00	45	0.08									
12:18:00	50	0.08									
12:20:00	50	0.08									
12:20:01											End of Run 6
12:35:48	300	0.09	80	15							Start Profile 3 from 50'
12:37:24	225	0.07		20							FL010
12:38:30	60	0.15	149	1000							FL020
12:39:11	15	0.08									End of Profile 3 @ 3000'
12:47:53											Start Run 7 @ 1300'
12:48:00	250	0.09	282	30							
12:50:00	220	0.08		25							
12:52:00	215	0.08		10							
12:54:00	230	0.08		10							
12:56:00	225	0.08		30							
12:57:52											End of Run 7
13:01:01											Start Run 8 @ 2250'
13:02:00	150	0.16	555	2000	1	75	12				
13:04:00	140	0.35	694	5000	2	50	12				
13:06:00	80	0.5	753	4000	4	75	12				
13:08:00	160	0.09	860	300							

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B095
Date: 13/05/2005

Campaign Name: CLOPAP
Operator: M. Nielsdottir (UEA)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
			FL110 NOxy calibration	
10:00:35	10:01:35	1	Same time as calibration but pressure seems fine. TEST BOTTLE	3.22
10:28:30			Start profile 1 (ascending)	
10:31:32			End profile 1	
10:39:29			Start run 1 at 1000 ft	
10:42:23	10:43:23	2	Below clouds over sea	3.62
10:44:27	10:45:27	3	Closer to cloud base (some through cloud)	3.62
10:49:48			End run 1	
10:52:44			Start run 2 at 1800 ft	
10:56:56	10:57:56	4	Through wispy cloud	3.56
10:59:30	11:00:30	5		3.58
11:02:45			End run 2	
11:05:53			Start run 3 at 2700 ft	
11:10:08	11:11:08	6	Above cloud	3.56
11:12:42	11:13:42	7		3.55
11:15:54			End run 3	
11:41:18			(LEG 2) Start run 4 at 1500 ft	
11:42:43	11:43:43	8	Below clouds	3.61
11:45:35	11:46:35	9		3.61
11:51:16			End run 4	
11:54:47			Start run 5 at 2050 ft	
11:56:07	11:57:07	10	In cloud	3.56
12:01:01	12:02:01	11		3.58
12:04:47			End run 5	
12:09:05			Start run 6 at 3100 ft	

12:16:41	12:17:41	12	Above cloud	3.54
12:18:46	12:19:46	13		3.54
12:20:00	12:21:00		End run 6	
12:35:50			LEG 3 Start profile	
12:39:10			End profile at 3000 ft	
12:47:53			Start run 7 at 1300 ft (below cloud)	
12:49:48	12:50:48	14	Below cloud	
12:53:23	12:54:23	15		
12:57:03			End run 7	
13:01:01			Start run 8 at 2200 ft	
13:01:39	13:02:39	16	In cloud	3.58
13:06:01	13:07:01	17		3.58
13:14:05			Start run 9 at 3000 ft	
13:17:57	13:18:57	18	Above cloud	3.55
13:21:02	13:22:02	19		3.56
13:26:33			End run 9	
13:32:24		20	FL100 same as NOxy calibration	3.31

Tinlet taken as sample is being pumped in!

Flight No B095

CCNC LOG

Exp. CLOPAP

Max time offset 1 sec

Date 13/15/05

Page 1 of

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	Tinlet	19.77	19.85	STATIC	19.99	20.04		REMARKS
ON	OFF		Drum	16.03	15.36	19.94 19.46	13.76	12.57		
				1	2	3	4	5		
10:39:31	10:40:00	1400		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
			1 20.04	0.54	0.77	1.15	1.5	2.19	S	Run 1 below cloud
			2 20.2	680	660	943	1107	1401	D	
			3 20.2	497	489	503	524	524	B	alt 1400m
			4 20.2	2302	2280	2276	2286	2310	R	
			5 20.38	1011.4	1012.5	1012.6	1012.2	1012.1	P	top Bottom
Run 2 above cloud										
11:07:40	11:08:10	2500	1 21.85	0.54	0.75	1.17	1.48	2.17	S	21.86 17.96
			2 20.4	454	525	678	625	717	D	21.75 18.85
			3 21.6	470	472	478	476	490	B	21.5 16.0
			4 21.4	2307	2313	2348	2364	2375	R	21.6 15.4
			5 21.8	1012.4	1012.3	1012.3	1012.3	1012.3	P	21.5 14.0
Run 3 above cloud										
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		Run 4 below cloud
11:41:47	11:42:15	1500	1 22.95	0.51	0.75	1.1	1.43	2.1	S	22.6 19.0
			2 22.84	829	823	1057	1329	1759	D	22.73 16.25
			3 22.85	576	578	605	653	742	B	22.75 17.26
			4 22.7	2399	2389	2376	2370	2356	R	22.74 16.47
			5 22.3	1011.5	1011.5	1011.5	1011.7	1011.7	P	22.72 15.19
Run 5 above cloud										
12:09:30	12:10:00	3500	1 23.7	0.5	0.73	1.11	1.43	2.07	S	23.5 19.8
			2 23.05	603	943	920	1085	1829	D	23.55 18.98
			3 22.95	541	538	573	681	697	B	23.52 17.99
			4 22.9	2351	2361	2391	2411	2430	R	23.52 17.26
			5 22.89	1010.9	1010.9	1010.9	1010.9	1011.0	P	23.49 15.99
Run 6 above cloud										
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		Run 7 below cloud
12:48:00	12:48:29	1300	1 23.9	0.5	0.72	1.09	1.41	2.07	S	24.12 20.4
			2 23.9	1045	976	1343	1657	733	D	24.2 19.69
			3 23.5	586	574	585	618	683	B	24.36 18.65
			4 23.3	2415	2408	2402	2381	2371	R	24.04 17.8
			5 23.4	1012.2	1012.2	1012.3	1012.3	1012.4	P	24.0 16.5
Run 8 above cloud										
13:16:24	13:16:54	3000	1 24.0	0.5	0.72	1.1	1.4	2.06	S	24.45 20.75
			2 23.5	551	837	6010	1129	1680	D	24.5 20.05
			3 23.8	542	539	556	576	618	B	24.5 18.99
			4 24.0	2316	2298	2297	2318	2319	R	24.5 18.25
			5 23.4	1012.5	1012.4	1012.5	1012.5	1012.5	P	24.42 16.9

LUBRICANT
Value not
open properly

19.8

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B095**

Date: 13/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	Y
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	Y	PTRMS		N
PERCA	Y	N	Bag Sampling		N
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B095

Date: 13/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. CCN data problem still present.
3. ADA laser failure during first science run.

Aircraft

1. Comms box/headsets possible intermittent defect – less noticeable later in flight.